

Investigating the Factors Affecting Turkey's Wheat Flour Export Leadership with K-Means Clustering and Discriminant Analysis

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Abstract

Some countries have important roles in the production of certain agricultural products depending on their geographical conditions. However, the rankings of countries may change over time due to natural factors (temperature, rainfall) and political reasons (wars, economic situation). Turkey holds an important position in the world in wheat production and is also among the leading countries in wheat flour exports. This study examines the main factors influencing Türkiye's role in wheat flour exports and evaluates their impact on export strategies. Data from Trade Map and other international databases covering 2023 wheat flour trade for 105 countries were analysed using multivariate statistical methods (MSM), including Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA), K-Means Clustering (KMCA), and Discriminant Analysis (DA). HCA was applied to group and examine the data more accurately and to determine the number of clusters. After dividing the data, K-Means Cluster Analysis was applied for optimization and separation the countries into 6 clusters. Discriminant Analysis was then used to identify the functions and indicators, most effective in forming these clusters. The sequential analyses provided more accurate interpretations and evaluations. Both K-Means Cluster Analysis and Discriminant Analysis results were compatible, showing that the factors most affecting Türkiye's wheat flour exports are population and currency change rate. These findings offer valuable insights for trade and economic policymakers aiming to strengthen Turkey's strategic role in global wheat flour exports.

Keywords: Hierarchical cluster analysis, k-means clustering, discriminant analysis, wheat flour

1. Introduction

The importance of exports, which is one of the important elements of foreign trade, for the economy of countries is a fact that cannot be ignored. Export is basically defined as the sale of the products or services produced by countries in the international market and earning income in the currencies of other countries. In addition to countries earning income by exporting, the increase in exports increases the capacity utilization rate and thus there is a decrease in average unit costs. In addition, exports encourage the implementation of policies for technological developments. Increasing exports enables the increase in capacity utilization rate, the decrease in average unit costs, the implementation of policies for technological developments, the introduction and sale of domestic products to the world, the creation of new job opportunities and the reduction of unemployment (Doğruyol et al., 2020). The demand for food, which is essential for the continuation of life and therefore permanent, also has an important place in world trade (Palacioğlu, 2022). Food Industry is the main sector that is the basic need for human life along with health. Food export, which is one of the types of exports, is an important area of economic activity and a great source of income for many countries. Food exports generally include processed or unprocessed agricultural products, local delicacies, seafood, cereals, vegetables and fruits, spices, oils and oil seeds. Cereals (wheat, barley, corn, oats, rice, rye, etc.) are the leading food exports. Each country has its own special methods that they use or implement to reach their targeted export figures in international trade. Databases that provide access to international trade data are one of these methods. With the information they obtain from these databases, companies can get information about the countries they want to export to, learn the average prices of similar products, and determine which category they are in the product market with their products technologically. Some of these frequently used databases are Turk Stat (Turkish Statistical Institute), Undersecretariats of Foreign Trade, World

Bank, Trade Map, Eurostat. In Trade Map Database has been determined that Türkiye is the leader in wheat flour exports in the world. In this study, it was aimed to determine the factors that are effective in the formation of this leadership and to evaluate them in our economic and commercial policies. It has been determined that some of the effective factors on wheat flour exports are Türkiye's strategic location, high production capacity, the product being the main food source and therefore high demand, the product's pricing policy and price changes depending on the currencies of the countries. Within the scope of this study, detailed research were carried out, and data sets were obtained for the wheat flour product, which is the 110100 HS coded product of 105 countries, from the Trade Map, GAIN (Global Agricultural Information Network), World Population, Current Converter databases published in 2023. Subsequently, data such as export, production amounts, average distances of countries to the countries they export to, unit price paid for a ton of wheat flour, population amounts of countries, wheat flour import values and exchange rate were reached. For the statistical analysis, Hierarchical Clustering Analysis, which is one of the multivariate statistical analysis techniques, followed by K-Means Clustering Analysis and Discriminant Analysis, were applied to 7 variables, respectively. The results of this study revealed the picture of Türkiye's wheat flour trade. The obtained data provides a strategic and commercial guidance service for Türkiye to develop its trade policies and maintain its export leadership.

1.1. Exporting of wheat and wheat flour

The agricultural sector is one of the most mentioned sectors in the world in recent years due to reasons such as climate change, wars, chaos and increases in food prices. Wheat, which is one of the most produced, needed, basic nutrients and raw material of some industrial products as agricultural production, is one of the first cereals that come to mind. Wheat also contributes essential amino acids, minerals, and vitamins, and beneficial phytochemicals and dietary fibre components

to the human diet, and these are particularly enriched in whole-grain products (Shewry, 2009). As can be seen from the literature and statistical data, wheat is a very valuable agricultural product as it is an indispensable food source, an important export item, a raw material with a wide range of products that can be transformed and processed, and its ability to direct the economies of countries. In addition to flour production, wheat also plays a leading role in the production of products such as bread, cookies, pasta, biscuits, semolina, bran, animal feed, beer, vinegar and starch. The reason for choosing these sectors is that Türkiye is the number one exporter of wheat flour in the international market and one of the top five in pasta (Çaşkurlu, 2023). In the literature, emphasis has been found on many different areas such as the importance of wheat and wheat flour in Türkiye and the world, pricing studies on wheat and wheat flour, government policies to support production and exports, and production estimates. In addition, the effects of natural and human factors such as natural disasters, global warming, wars, economic crises on wheat and wheat flour production and export in Türkiye and in the world have also been the subject of the studies. This studies also emphasized the importance of wheat, ways to increase its sustainability, and the importance of producing better quality wheat with less pesticides. The amount of wheat production in the world and in Türkiye has been evaluated and the policies supporting this wheat production between the European Union and Türkiye have been compared. If Türkiye cannot strengthen and develop its agricultural policy by making the necessary reforms, when it becomes a full member of the EU and agricultural products are put into free circulation, it will not be possible for it to compete with the EU with its current structure, and Türkiye will become an open market for agricultural products to the EU (Kızılaslan, 2004). This study evaluates in detail the conditions (political, economic and social reasons, environmental conditions, etc.) that ensure self-sufficiency in wheat production and foreign trade in Türkiye. Climate-adapted agricultural techniques that prioritize

environmental impacts, especially sustainable soil and water policy tools can be used for sustainable quality wheat production. Studies have been conducted on the position and importance of the bakery products industry in Türkiye, and evaluations have been made as a result of these studies, highlighting the challenges faced by the industry. The most important problems of the sector are the inability to supply raw materials in the required quality, standard and quantity, the lack of qualified labor, the necessity to fight against unfair competition due to small business structures and the informal economy, the constant increase in production costs, etc. (Özaydın and Karakayacı, 2023). This study also implemented the effective role of Türkiye's membership in the Customs Union and the implementation of the inward processing regime on wheat and wheat flour exports. As a result of the study, it was observed that the inward processing regime was inevitable due to the low capacity utilization rate in the sector, and accordingly, wheat imports and wheat product exports increased, and future estimates and suggestions were put forward for the increase in wheat production and wheat product exports. Import is inevitable for the effective operation of the installed capacity in the bakery products sector, and importing within the scope of inward processing and exporting the final product allows the installed capacity not to remain idle and provides foreign exchange inflow (Duru et al., 2019). After the Russia-Ukraine war, the wheat export effects of the Black Sea grain corridor agreement were evaluated, and it was stated that this agreement had positive effects on wheat exports, albeit for a short time. The agreement also contributes to reducing food security concerns and alleviating food crises due to increased war (Bayazıt and Gürbüz, 2023). The competitiveness of Kazakhstan in wheat exports was mentioned, and it was emphasized that Kazakhstan should develop a policy regarding wheat quality, wheat production and export, since this power is gradually decreasing. In addition, it was stated that Central Asian countries (Kazakhstan,

Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan) accounted for 3 percent of global wheat production, evaluations were made on position of Russia in global wheat trade, and it was stated that Russia dominates 10 percent of global wheat trade. In order to increase wheat production rate in these countries, it is necessary to improve the agricultural structure, to spread the use of appropriate cultivation techniques, to increase irrigation opportunities and to raise awareness of producers about alternative production models (organic

farming, good agricultural practices, etc.) (Bashimov, 2021). As it is known, all goods produced and traded in the "harmonized system (HS)" used all over the world are indicated by the main identifier codes between 01 and 99. Under the 2-digit chapters, which are the main codes, the definition is gradually narrowed down with the final codes of 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 and the final definition is reached. The HS Code image of any product or item is shown below (Figure 1).

Figure 1. HS code of any product

While the HS Code is the same worldwide down to the first six digits, countries can refine it to suit their own needs. For example, countries can integrate such breakdowns into their systems to obtain detailed statistics and apply customs duties on a more specific product basis. Countries can use this code with 6 digits or more digits if they deem it sufficient. Each number has a specific meaning. The first 2 digits indicate the position number of the goods, the first 6 digits show the code used by all member countries of the "World Customs

Organization", the first 7-8 digits refer the code used by EU countries, the 9th-10th digits represent "positions opened due to different tax practices", and the 11th-12th digits give the final Customs Tariff Statistics (HS) code, which means that an item can be defined in the same way all over the world. The HS code of the wheat flour we included in our study has been determined as 110100 (Wheat Flour), and our data set, which includes the TradeMap Wheat flour export data for 2023, is also stated in Table 1.

Table 1. Data set used in the study

No	Contries	Export	Distance	Unit Price	Population	Import	Exchange Rate	Production
1	Türkiye	1497903	2938	486	84339067	28941	26.0396	17650000
2	Germany	494581	588	499	83783942	60558	0.91773	21459200
3	Uzbekistan	268530	668	343	33469203	141954	11.565	5984756
4	Italy	251904	3158	842	60461826	18194	0.91773	7294570
5	India	209495	6622	528	1380004385	1456	81.9887	109590000
6	Argentina	196729	1867	465	45195774	180	258.473	17644277
7	Canada	169301	1579	900	37742154	44294	1.32323	22296100
8	United States	163213	2538	803	331002651	294098	1	44790360
9	Belgium	155522	433	500	11589623	67194	0.91773	1629180
10	Kazakhstan	145762	766	333	18776707	357	447.88	11814123
11	Russian Federation	145058	2367	310	145934462	3726	89.7336	76057258
12	United Kingdom	137716	869	618	67886011	67916	0.78694	13988000
13	France	116302	2472	622	65273511	179080	0.91773	36559450
14	Egypt	115773	2851	664	102334404	3984	30.9355	9000000
15	Japan	98540	3402	596	126476461	4693	144.482	1097000
16	Viet Nam	94440	1300	436	97338579	8041	23708.3	0
17	Netherlands	92419	3474	674	17134872	294525	0.91773	947250
18	Hungary	81235	372	461	9660351	29530	344.367	5290140
19	Slovakia	68170	259	449	5459642	35351	0.91773	2002240
20	China	67521	1235	480	1439323776	55940	7.22298	136952000
21	Spain	64425	994	551	46754778	91285	0.91773	8564630
22	Serbia	60298	242	458	8737371	1986	107.718	3442308
23	Poland	60146	979	544	37846661	63861	4.0665	11893550
24	Dominican Republic	58004	245	712	10847910	2824	55.6877	0
25	South Africa	42729	846	623	59308690	20026	18.6988	2257205
26	Rwanda	39334	717	743	12952218	1051	1171.8	13684
27	Austria	34998	432	585	9006398	53173	0.91773	1547600
28	Bulgaria	34181	595	513	6948445	6071	1.79492	7342990
29	Sri Lanka	33710	2417	47	21413249	113436	308.232	0
30	Portugal	33637	1803	714	10196709	58935	0.91773	69440
31	Jordan	32851	284	664	10203134	3164	0.709	3000
32	Indonesia	32426	3345	544	273523615	22141	15025.6	0
33	Malaysia	31382	642	576	32365999	50661	4.65842	0
34	Korea	29565	4985	763	77048001	14408	1298.93	116603
35	Mexico	26472	1422	665	128932753	100592	17.0447	3283613
36	Ukraine	24235	1449	318	43733762	1549	37.1807	32183300
37	United Arab Emirates	23698	4959	422	9890402	13647	3.6736	30
38	Latvia	21251	2967	516	1886198	4737	0.6449	2407700
39	Czech Republic	21104	329	580	10708981	50946	21.7795	4960930
40	Greece	19193	846	618	10423054	15954	0.91773	1058360
41	Luxembourg	18468	289	517	625978	7797	37.021	76140
42	Lesotho	16364	369	561	2142249	16441	18.6988	6000
43	El Salvador	16364	223	643	6486205	9612	1	0
44	Honduras	16055	379	682	9904607	16062	25.0289	1255
45	Australia	14190	4699	716	25499884	15717	1.49599	31922554
46	Brazil	13875	4071	705	212559417	137627	4.81816	7874
47	Thailand	13218	1820	811	69799978	86742	34.9504	1317
48	Paraguay	9442	1338	493	7132538	8	7371.04	927776
49	Algeria	9299	2456	278	43851044	5390	136.185	2168386
50	Burundi	9110	667	785	11890784	515	2851.32	8806
51	Bosnia and Herzegovina	8997	597	570	3280819	19924	1.79492	314382
52	Ghana	8970	814	420	31072940	23244	11.3927	0
53	Denmark	8718	982	654	5792202	33536	6.83518	4047090
54	Croatia	8074	267	523	4105267	16581	6.91463	986930

55	Romania	7733	1197	552	19273691	78127	4.54874	10433750
56	Lithuania	7456	1631	528	2722289	23407	0.91773	4248850
57	Switzerland	7149	484	964	8654622	11566	0.89639	401202
58	Slovenia	6023	2435	591	2078938	12038	219.924	154450
59	Guatemala	5878	318	633	17915568	29560	8.02098	291
60	Colombia	5376	1061	731	50882891	526	4173.88	6965
61	Uruguay	4834	2165	552	3473730	1512	37.9268	936400
62	Estonia	4816	1558	459	1326535	3461	0.91773	736270
63	Sweden	4639	695	784	10099265	9526	10.8314	3027800
64	Ireland	3918	1015	733	4937786	141671	0.91773	628080
65	Côte d'Ivoire	3645	708	483	26378274	3	601.989	0
66	Cameroon	3528	810	257	26545863	6083	601.989	633
67	Mozambique	3507	533	644	31255435	639	64.46	15000
68	Moldova	3435	307	342	4033963	10757	18.5708	1565200
69	Finland	3379	1035	462	5540720	3194	0.91773	687160
70	Yemen	3161	3035	445	29825964	166274	250.826	125000
71	New Zealand	3127	7407	825	4822233	6402	1.61815	422831
72	Peru	2260	1012	561	32971854	1032	3.67684	202725
73	Lebanon	2251	4484	299	6825445	10061	15050.38	100000
74	Jamaica	2014	2057	900	2961167	496	155.705	0
75	Oman	2005	2803	359	5106626	500	0.38619	3542
76	Cyprus	1116	2406	627	1207359	3714	0.91773	25580
77	Israel	996	9830	664	8655535	12038	3.70841	150000
78	Nepal	909	4460	633	29136808	9	132.663	2127276
79	Morocco	802	3263	620	36910560	222	9.97089	7543847
80	Kenya	775	1552	798	53771296	182	141.648	245300
81	Tanzania	539	728	442	59734218	5306	2429.52	70000
82	Bangladesh	532	4779	636	164689383	719	109.491	1085368
83	Macedonia	317	603	314	2083374	22636	56.983	243676
84	Chile	314	5653	653	19116201	10974	799.412	1353607
85	Georgia	238	1687	486	3989167	68116	2.63	135900
86	Kuwait	203	1198	728	4270571	1049	0.30804	36
87	Albania	166	751	532	2877797	9936	97.9336	225170
88	Pakistan	128	7372	298	220892340	13735	282.884	27464081
89	Iraq	93	1191	705	40222493	612636	1335.86	4233714
90	Norway	89	641	2119	5421241	4795	10.6666	266600
91	Belarus	88	749	260	9449323	249	2.5147	2441000
92	Tunisia	83	1976	764	11818619	263	3.11239	1193000
93	Ethiopia	65	7599	333	114963588	28529	55.1554	5214000
94	Kyrgyzstan	63	369	313	6524195	12485	87.3782	362711
95	Madagascar	43	885	478	27691018	59612	4588.8	2000
96	Nigeria	29	684	48	206139589	261	770.155	90000
97	Iceland	22	778	1158	341243	4139	137.109	0
98	Congo	21	1080	309	5518087	176	2431	9000
99	Namibia	12	11656	462	2540905	314	18.6988	18377
100	Azerbaijan	11	1900	440	10139177	9911	1.7	1837188
101	Niger	8	684	308	24206644	18425	770.155	4628
102	Zambia	8	1207	727	18383955	202	17.793	205881
103	Guyana	7	7244	2333	786552	677	220.465	0
104	Armenia	4	1607	100	2963243	11205	406.025	97000
105	Equator	3	2806	600	1402985	9651	601.989	10898

The HS Code is a code obtained from the World Customs Organization and is a system where detailed information can be obtained about the products exported or imported from all over the world. If the HS code of the product you are looking for is unknown, or if you do not know which product the current code you have belongs to, we can determine it by searching by word from <https://uygulama.gtb.gov.tr/> Tara address or by searching with the HS code. It is very important to determine the HS code correctly. If the code is detected incorrectly, the process cannot proceed correctly, as taxation and examination processes will be initiated according to the product to be imported. Before exporting the product, exporters should perform market research, determine the HS code of the product correctly, and decide the export policies according to the obtained data. In the literature, there have been many studies on cluster analysis, K-means cluster analysis, hierarchical clustering analysis and discriminant analysis, some of which are mentioned below. In order to determine the best location for the selection of a religious facility in the Melikgazi district of Kayseri, a determination study was carried out with the K-Means clustering analysis method. The location of the facility is planned according to the place where the clustering is the most intense and the distance between the clusters is the least (Özmerdivenli et al., 2021). By calculating the biogas potential from animal wastes in Düzce province and districts, it was tried to divide the facilities into clusters according to their location with the k-means clustering method. It is a study carried out to determine the location of the facility that gives the smallest value to the sum of Euklid Distances (Yürük and Erdoğan, 2015). In another study on clustering techniques in data mining, a clustering study was carried out with the K-means Method in the database that includes country flags (Sarıman, 2011). In the study conducted on the determination of the relationship between the self-esteem of the university students and the attitude of the parents by discriminant analysis, a

questionnaire study was applied and the results were evaluated by discriminant analysis, and the parental attitude was categorized and assigned (Filiz, 2011). In addition, there are informative studies on quadratic discriminant analysis that we used in our study. In the study on quadratic discriminant analysis and error rate estimation, information was given on the importance of quadratic discriminant analysis and in which situations it can be used (Akbaba, 2005). In a study conducted on academicians, discriminant analysis was applied in order to determine which variable was effective in this distinction by considering 17 different variables according to certain characteristics such as gender, title, and marital status. In academic sources, many factors such as wheat types, the effect of wheat types on yield, wheat quality, and comparison of protein amounts in wheat types have been studied. In these studies, different bread wheat varieties were evaluated in terms of their agricultural characteristics and quality characteristics, and in order to better understand the subject, cluster analysis was performed and data were classified (Kahrıman and Egesel, 2011). In order to determine genetic differences in some durum wheat varieties grown in Türkiye, the RAPD method was used and it was determined that there was a narrow genetic difference between wheat varieties (Çiftçi and Yağdı, 2011). The protein ratios in bread flour, wheat flour, and bran were compared, and it was determined that the average protein ratio in wheat grain was higher than in wheat flour and lower than in wheat bran (Şahin et al., 2016).

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Data collection

One of the sources used for the data used in this study is the "Trade Map" (anonymus, 2024) database. From this database, export, import, unit price, average distance to export countries of 105 countries from the world were obtained. The world export map of the product mentioned in the study is shown below (Figure 2).

Figure 2. World wheat flour export value map for 2023

To calculate country production amounts is GAIN (Global Agricultural Information Network) (Anonymus, 2024a) database, to access the population data of the countries (Anonymus, 2024b) database, and to learn the fees that countries will pay to buy a dollar in their own currencies the (Anonymus, 2024c) database were used. Data from 105 countries are listed in Tablo 1. Since the factors that are effective in Turkey's leadership in wheat flour exports, which is the main aim of our study, will be analyzed, these factors are stated below. All variables were standardized using Z-scores before statistical analysis to ensure comparability across different units and scales. The data collected and made ready for evaluation were examined with various analysis methods in the SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) program.

- Export values of countries (dependent; continuous, USD)
- Wheat flour production amounts of countries (independent; continuous, metric tons)

- Average distances of countries to the countries they export to (independent; continuous, kilometers)
- The price that countries pay for a ton of wheat flour (independent; continuous, USD/ton)
- Population of countries (independent; continuous, persons)
- Import values of countries (independent; continuous, USD)
- Currency exchange rate values of countries (independent; continuous) (local to USD)

2.2. Cluster analyses

Cluster analysis is an analysis method in which sampling or the main mass is grouped according to specified characteristics and ensures that the similarity between the groups is minimum and the similarity within the group is maximum. In the literature, cluster analysis is one of the most used methods and is preferred more frequently for problem-solving, data mining, image processing, and market research. Clustering analysis generally varies with different algorithms, including partition-based, constraint-based, hierarchical based,

model-based, density-based, and grid-based. In this study, we used partition-based K-Means clustering analysis to determine how many clusters we should divide our data into using hierarchical clustering analysis and to assign our data to k clusters.

2.2.1 Hierarchical clustering analysis

There are two types of hierarchical clustering methods; grouping and divisive methods. In the grouping hierarchical clustering analysis method (G-HCA), each unit or each observation is initially considered in a cluster, and the two closest clusters (or observations) are combined into a new cluster, called “Agglomerative Clustering”. Thus, the number of clusters is reduced by one at each step. The “Ward’s method” was chosen as the

linkage criterion to minimize the total within-cluster variance at each step. This process can be shown with a shape called a “dendrogram” or “tree graph”. In the divisive hierarchical clustering analysis method (D-HCA), the process is just the contrary of the G-HCA. In this method, a large cluster consisting of all observations is generated. Dissimilar observations are eliminated and smaller clusters are created (Çelik, 2013). While performing cluster analysis applications, if the researcher does not have any idea how many clusters the data should be divided into, he/she can obtain preliminary information with HCA. As an alternative to HCA, the number of clusters into which the data should be divided, can also be determined according to the heuristic formula given below.

$$k = \sqrt{\frac{n}{2}} \tag{Eqn. 1}$$

n: number of data to cluster

k: number of cluster

In cluster analysis applications, if the researcher has prior knowledge about the number of clusters or has already decided on the number of clusters to be meaningful, non-

hierarchical methods can also be preferred (Ergün et al., 2024). In our study, hierarchical clustering analysis technique was applied to obtained data set with the Ward method. In the Ward method, the sum of squared errors is presented in the equation below.

$$Ess = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i)^2}{n} \tag{Eqn. 2}$$

xi : nth observation value

n : defined data

2.2.2 K-means clustering analysis

The most popular clustering algorithm, the K-Means technique, was developed by Macqueen in 1967 (Dündar, 2024). Before applying this method, the value of k should be determined. If the researcher knows the number of clusters in advance, he/she can use the "k" value; if not, he can obtain this value with HCA or its formulation. The K-Means algorithm works as follows:

- The center of the K-clusters is determined randomly.

- By calculating the smallest square Euclidean distance between centers and observations, each observation is assigned to the nearest center of gravity. The least square Euclidean distance between the assigned center and the observation should be minimal with respect to the other centers.

- The centers of the formed clusters are determined.
- The distances for each data point are redetermined, and the data is reassigned to the nearest cluster.
- This work is applied repeatedly until the cluster centers approach a stable equilibrium (Çelik and Cömertler, 2021).

In this analysis method, a random cluster center is determined from the data generated in the first assignment. The distances between each data and the cluster center are calculated and then, new cluster centers are identified. The algorithm continues the calculations until all data are evaluated within the groups and the optimization occurs. As a result of the analysis, the clustering with the lowest SSE (The sum of squares error) value gives the best result (Çelik and Cömertler, 2021) (Eqn 2.) The quality of clustering was evaluated using the ANOVA F-statistics, which reflect the importance of each variable in differentiating the clusters.

$$y = c + a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + \dots + a_nx_n \quad (\text{Eqn. 3})$$

where, y is the dependent variable, c is the constant of the equation, x_n and a_n represent to the n^{th} independent variable and the discriminant coefficient of the n^{th} independent variable, respectively (Eqn. 3). DA is also used to determine the group of a unit, even if it is unknown which group it comes from with minimal error. The assumptions of discriminant analysis are as follows:

- Normal distribution: The independent variables should be in accordance with the normal distribution. Normality testing can be used to verify this.
- Homogeneity of variance covariance matrix: The covariance matrix in each group should be homogeneous.
- Outliers: DA is sensitive to outliers. There should be no outliers in the data set.
- Multiple linear linkage: There should be no multicollinearity between variables.
- There shouldn't be very high correlation ($r > 0.80$) between variables (Çelik and Cömertler, 2021). These assumptions provide a mathematical model to apply DA. In the data

2.2.3 Discriminant analysis

Discriminant analysis (DA) is a statistical technique that allows simultaneous analysis of differences between two or more sample groups according to various variables. Discriminant obtained from discriminant analysis consist of linear components of predictor variables. Discriminant functions reveal the effects of the predictor variables that cause the difference between groups and enable the most influential variable to be identified (Burmaoglu et al., 2009). The formula of the discriminant function can be expressed as:

set where DA is applied, the dependent variable (criterion variable) should have categorical data and it is always classified over independent metric variables. In this study, initially, "Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA)" was considered, but due to the violation of the homogeneity of variance-covariance matrices (as confirmed by the Box's M test), "Quadratic Discriminant Analysis (QDA)" was performed instead.

3. Results

3.1. Hierarchical clustering analysis

For the hierarchical clustering analysis, the values of the independent variables (countries' wheat flour production amounts, the populations of countries, the amount of imports, etc.) were standardized by using the z-score. HCA was created using the Ward clustering method to determine the number of clusters into which the countries would be separated. The dendrogram graph obtained at the end of the analysis is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Dendrogram generated as a result of hierarchical clustering analysis

It is clearly seen from this graph that the optimal number of clusters for our data set is six, due to the fact that the values are very close to each other and more objects will be added to each set. In addition, the Eqn. 1 was evaluated for 105 countries in our data set and a result of 7 was obtained.

3.2. K-Means clustering analysis

After determining the number of clusters (6 clusters for our study), K-Means cluster analysis was used to determine which country belongs to which cluster. As in HCA, in this part of the study, the analysis was carried out with standardized scores (Z-Scores) of the variables. The obtained results are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Cluster analysis statistical results table

Factors	Anova					
	Cluster		Error			
	MS	df	MS	df	F	Sig.
Production amounts	14.54	5	0.32	99	46.02	< 0.001
Average distances of countries to the contries	13.48	5	0.37	99	36.43	< 0.001
Unit price paid for a ton of wheat flour	11.78	5	0.46	99	25.85	< 0.001
Population amounts of countries	19.33	5	0.07	99	260.07	< 0.001
Wheat flour import values	13.67	5	0.36	99	37.95	< 0.001
Exchange rate	17.67	5	0.16	99	113.00	< 0.001

MS: Mean Square, df: Degrees of Freedom, F: Anova Basic Test Statistic, Sig.: Significant Value

According to ANOVA results, each significant value (sig.) is below to 0.05 (See Table 2). This means that the results indicate that all independent variables included in the

clustering are effective and significant in terms of clustering. Furthermore, if one or more of the values were greater than 0.05, we would

have to state that the variables had no effect on clustering. The F-statistics reveal that:

- Population was the most influential factor (F=260.07)
- Followed by Currency Exchange Rate (F=113,0). Other variables also contributed significantly but with lower F-values. Table 3

shows the number of countries per cluster. While 82 countries were assigned to the first cluster, 2 countries were assigned to the second cluster, 3 countries to the third cluster, 3 countries to the fourth cluster, 12 countries to the fifth cluster, and 3 countries to the sixth cluster. There are no countries that are not included in the clustering.

Table 3. Clusters obtained as a result of k-means cluster analysis

Clusters	Countries	Number of Countries in Cluster
Cluster 1	Iceland, Jamaica, Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, El Salvador, Malaysia, Sri Lanka, Dominican Republic, Kuwait, Guatemala, Cameroon, Honduras, Thailand, Madagascar, Oman, Niger, Lesotho, Colombia, Burundi, Congo, Rwanda, Mozambique, Cyprus, Jordan, Portugal, Tanzania, Luxembourg, Nigeria, Armenia, Yemen, Georgia, Slovenia, Peru, Zambia, Albania, North Macedonia, Kenya, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kyrgyzstan, Switzerland, Ireland, Finland, Estonia, Paraguay, Uruguay, Croatia, Greece, Japan, Tunisia, Austria, Moldova, Belgium, Azerbaijan, Slovakia, Algeria, South Africa, Latvia, Belarus, Sweden, Mexico, Serbia, Denmark, Lithuania, Czechia, Hungary, Uzbekistan, Italy, Bulgaria, Morocco, Spain, Egypt, Romania, Kazakhstan, Poland, United Kingdom, Argentina, Turkey, Germany, Canada, Ukraine, France, Russia	82
Cluster 2	India, China	2
Cluster 3	Netherlands, Iraq, United States	3
Cluster 4	Guyana, Ecuador, Norway	3
Cluster 5	United Arab Emirates, Brazil, Namibia, South Korea, Israel, New Zealand, Bangladesh, Chile, Nepal, Ethiopia, Pakistan, Australia	12
Cluster 6	Indonesia, Vietnam, Lebanon	3
Sum of Countries		105

As can be seen from the Table 3, this imbalance in clustering indicates that hierarchical preclustering or alternative linkage methods could provide a more uniform

clustering. This is believed to provide direction for future studies. In Figure 4, the visualized version of the table 3 can be seen as a graph.

Figure 4. Distribution plot of variables according to the result of k-means clustering analysis

The second cluster, which includes China and India, was influenced by the population amounts and wheat flour production amounts of the countries, while the third cluster, which includes the Netherlands, Iraq and the USA, was influenced by the wheat flour import values of the countries. In the same way, the price of one ton of wheat flour was effective in the formation of the 4th cluster, including Guyana, Ecuador and Norway, and the average

distance between the countries was influential in the formation of the 5th cluster, which consists of 12 countries. Additionally, the exchange rate was an effective factor in the formation of the 6th cluster, which includes Indonesia, Vietnam and Lebanon (Figure 4). Table 4 shows the numerical value of the cluster center for each variable of each 6 cluster as a result of the analysis.

Table 4. Final cluster centers

Factors	Clusters					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Production Amounts	-0.13	5.91	0.49	-0.35	-0.06	-0.36
Average Distances of Countries to the Countries	-0.38	0.88	0.17	0.83	2.07	0.47
Unit Price Paid for a Ton of Wheat Flour	-0.15	-0.29	0.45	4.30	0.00	-0.55
Population Amounts of Countries	-0.19	6.82	0.33	-0.29	0.05	0.31
Wheat Flour Import Values	-0.11	-0.10	4.69	-0.44	-0.20	-0.30
Exchange Rate	-0.15	-0.25	-0.13	-0.24	-0.20	5.35

In the K-Means cluster analysis, Anova test was applied to evaluate the degree of influence and significance of each of the 6 factors used in the cluster analysis on the clustering process and to determine the most effective factor (Table 5). In K-Means clustering analysis, the

Anova table showing which of the 6 factors used in the clustering analysis had a significant effect on the clustering process and which factor had the greatest effect is shown in Table 5.

Table 5. K-means cluster analysis anova test results

Factor	F	p-Value
Production amounts	46.02	<0.001
Average distances of countries to the countries	36.43	<0.001
Unit price paid for a ton of wheat flour	25.85	<0.001
Population amounts of countries	260.07	<0.001
Wheat flour import values	37.95	<0.001
Exchange rate	113.00	<0.001

F: Anova Basic Test Statistic, p-Value: Probability Value

The test results showed that all 6 factors included in the cluster analysis were statistically significant on the cluster analysis ($p < 0.05$). The factor that had the greatest impact on the process of dividing countries into clusters was population ($F = 260.071$) followed by the rate of currency exchange ($F = 113.000$). Although the factors of production amount, average distance, price per ton of product, and import amount also had statistically significant effects, their effects were found to be less.

3.3. Discriminant analysis

In the last step of the statistical analysis, discriminant analysis was carried out to determine the discriminant function that distinguishes the 6 groups obtained as a result of cluster analysis. When the data were evaluated to test the normality assumption which is important for the discriminant analysis it was determined that the real score or standardized z-score, skewness and kurtosis values of the variables were outside the range of -2 and +2, and the normality test result did not show a normal distribution because the p-values were below 0.05. For this reason, the assumption of normality of the discriminant analysis was achieved by applying various transformations to the original data. Discriminant analysis was maintained with the data obtained by transformation. Another important assumption of discriminant analysis,

the absence of multiple linearities, was also checked by examining the correlation matrix between variables. In this statistical analysis, no variable couples showing a correlation relationship above 0.80 were found. This clearly demonstrates that there is no multilinearity problem in the data and that the discriminant analysis results are reliable. According to the results of linear discriminant analysis, it was determined that the test statistic was 256.052 as a result of the Box-M test and the associated significance level was less than 0.001. This situation shows that the homogeneity assumption of variance-covariance matrices of the discriminant analysis is violated. For this reason, as a type of discriminant analysis, quadratic discriminant analysis was performed instead of linear discriminant analysis. Even if the data have a normal distribution, the quadratic discriminant analysis method can be used when the variance-covariance matrices of the groups are different. Studies in the literature have shown that linear discriminant analysis gives more accurate results when calculations are made with separate groups. According to the results of the linear discriminant analysis with different settings, it was found that all independent variables had a significant predictive power in predicting which cluster the countries belonged to. The results of the analysis regarding the equality of group means can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. Discriminant analysis Anova test results

Factor	Wilk's lambda	F	p-Value
Production amounts	0.30	46.02	<0.001
Average distances of countries to the countries	0.35	36.43	<0.001
Unit price paid for a ton of wheat flour	0.43	25.85	<0.001
Population amounts of countries	0.07	260.07	<0.001
Wheat flour import values	0.34	37.95	<0.001
Exchange rate	0.15	113.00	<0.001

Wilk's Lambda: The Discriminatory Power of Variables for Groups, F: Anova Basic Test Statistic, p-Value: Probability Value

The results of the analysis regarding the equality of group means are parallel to the results of the K-Means cluster analysis (Table 5 and Table 6). It is clearly seen that, discriminant analysis results are compatible with the results of the K-Means cluster analysis. In a grouping system with 6 clusters, the important factors are the population and currency change rate of the countries. The

variances explained by each of the canonical discriminant functions obtained as a result of the quadratic discriminant analysis are shown in Table 7. Since the discriminant function number 1 explained the most variance (55.7%), it was deemed appropriate to interpret the analyzes by considering this discriminant function.

Table 7. Eigenvalue and variance explained by canonical discriminant analysis functions

Function	(Eigenvalue)	Variance explained (%)
1	13.613	55.7
2	5.898	24.1
3	2.116	8.7
4	1.780	7.3
5	1.031	4.2

Eigenvalue: The Power of the Function to Separate Groups, Variance Explained: Contribution of the Function to the total Discriminatory Power

Table 8 shows the standardized function coefficients in the context of the canonical discriminant function number one for each independent variable. In this table, only the coefficients of function 1, which explains the most variance, should be considered. Accordingly, in line with the findings of the previous analysis, it was found that the highest coefficient belonged to the rate of exchange of currency with the population. The coefficients of population amounts of countries in function 1 is greater than the other variables (Table 8).

This means that this variable has more influence on the first discriminant function than the other variables and has the greatest influence on the wheat flour exports. Similarly, currency change rates in function 2, wheat flour import values in function 3, wheat flour import values in function 4, and unit price variables paid per 1 ton of wheat flour in function 5 have the greatest impact on the formation of Turkey's wheat flour export leadership.

Table 8. Standardized canonical discriminant function coefficients

Variable	Function				
	1	2	3	4	5
Production Amounts	-0.04	-0.02	-0.03	0.10	0.12
Average Distances of Countries	0.16	0.24	0.65	-0.53	-0.50
Unit Price Paid for a Ton of Wheat Flour	0.06	-0.03	0.42	-0.33	0.85
Population Amounts of Countries	1.01	-0.12	-0.06	-0.01	0.01
Wheat Flour Import Values	0.01	0.05	0.70	0.72	-0.05
Exchange Rate	0.18	0.99	-0.04	0.07	0.11

Considering the 1st function from the standardized canonical discriminant function coefficients shown in Table 8, the equation of the discriminant analysis can be written as follows:

$$y = a + (-0.040 * \text{Production Amounts}) + (0.159 * \text{Average Distances of Countries to the Countries}) + (0.064 * \text{Unit Price Paid for a Ton of Wheat Flour}) + (1.008 * \text{Population Amounts of Countries}) + (0.010 * \text{Wheat Flour Import Values}) + (0.176 * \text{Exchange Rate})$$

In the final step of the analysis, the rate of correct estimation of the cluster to which the countries belong was examined by using the

quadratic discriminant analysis method. The number of countries in the clusters created by the cluster analysis is given in Table 9 and the number of countries assigned to the clusters through discriminant analysis was presented in the results of Estimated Group Membership. According to the table, 61 (74.4%) of the 82 countries in cluster 1 were correctly predicted, while 11 countries were predicted incorrectly as belonging to cluster 3, 8 countries to cluster 4, and 1 country each to cluster 5 and 6. The 2 countries in the 2nd cluster were also correctly estimated. It can be seen that the model accurately classified 74.3% of all countries.

Table 9. Table of the correct estimation of countries

Clusters		Estimated of Group Membership						Sum of group member
		1	2	3	4	5	6	
Number	1	61.00	0.00	11.00	8.00	1.00	1.00	82.00
	2	0.00	2.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.00
	3	0.00	0.00	3.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.00
	4	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.00	0.00	0.00	3.00
	5	0.00	0.00	5.00	1.00	6.00	0.00	12.00
	6	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.00	3.00
Percentage (%)	1	74.40	0.00	13.40	9.80	1.20	1.20	100.00
	2	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
	3	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
	4	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
	5	0.00	0.00	41.70	8.30	50.00	0.00	100.00
	6	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	100.00

Percentage of Correct Classification : 74.3 %

If countries were randomly assigned to clusters, this would correspond to a hit rate of 16.66% since there were 6 clusters in total, while the 74.3% accuracy rate obtained by the quadratic discriminant analysis method indicates a significant increase in success. In this instance, it confirms the ability of the variables used in the discriminant analysis to

meaningfully predict the grouping of countries into clusters.

4. Conclusion

The study aims to investigate why Turkey is the leader in wheat flour exports, to focus on the factors that provide this leadership, and to

provide important information to policy makers and economists with the results obtained. It has been determined that the two variables that best explain Turkey's leading position in wheat flour exports, as the results of the Discriminant Analysis specified in the study were compatible with the results of the K-Means Cluster Analysis, were "Populations of Countries and Currency Change Rates". When the results obtained are evaluated, Türkiye's ability to maintain, strengthen and sustain its leadership in wheat flour exports largely depends on the following parameters; (i) the purchasing or exporting power of target markets; (ii) the population dynamics of target markets and the population growth or decline rates; (iii) determining the correct and applicable pricing policy, and evaluating the changes in the exchange rate while determining this pricing policy; (iv) determining efficient policies on competition policy. In the future, the proposed method can be expanded by adding trade and customs union agreements of Turkey, applicable transportation infrastructures, determined taxes and tariffs, competition analyses.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare their contributions as follows: Conceptualization and Methodology were carried out jointly by DE and MÇG. Data curation, formal analysis, investigation, original draft preparation, visualization, project administration, and funding acquisition were conducted by MÇG. Supervision and review & editing were provided by DE.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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